

Performance of Sentimental Analysis by Studying and Mining Social Media using Parsing Technique

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ABSTRACT- The social media networks have evolved quickly and many people often use these services to communicate with others and categorise themselves by sharing their opinions, views and concepts. It is usually dispensed by winnowing the corresponding or interlinked events mentioned on social media websites like Twitter, Facebook, YouTube and Pinterest etc. A social media analysis has rapt from being a unidirectional to a bi-directional dialogue i.e. between generations to generation. The rudimentary objective behind such analyses is to see the extent of criticality with relation to criticism or appreciation delineated within the comments, tweets or blogs. This analysis shows how individuals assume, assess, talk and opine concerning completely different problems.

This paper focuses on the trend detection and analyse the emotions expressed in a specific sentence, paragraph or document. The opinions and sentiments are extracted from the collected data and it is fairly estimated based on the degree of quality. The principle contribution of this paper is to provide an outline for those who seek to utilize social media scraping and analytics using different software tools either in their analysis or business. In addition, the system design to implement the proposed idea has been discussed.

I.INTRODUCTION

The Social media is outlined as web and mobile-based applications that evolved into a vivacious platform wherever individuals communicate freely with one another, share concepts and discuss numerous events and problems. The Social media like Twitter, Facebook, Pinterest, YouTube, RSS feeds, blogs, wikis and news, are usually yielding unstructured text and are accessible through the web. A Trend analysis may be extremely useful to see how individuals assume and find emotions on social, non-secular or political problems. One reason for trend analysis may be to discover a nascent or suspicious behavior happening on the social media platform. For instance, analytic thinking may be accustomed however a bound team of individual area unit victimizes it to launch their information or facts concerning bound

political or non-secular problems. The Company sector can even use it to induce feedback concerning their merchandise.

The Social media trends are often generally classified into four varieties specifically positive, negative, neutral and uninterested. The level of trend will additionally be classified into low, medium, high which is able to primarily be connected to the vital comments or tweets. Sentiments are evaluated from the extracted social media content, which may either be in positive or negative perspective. The positive perspective of an individual is assumed as, he or she is happy with the content expressed by others on a certain issue. On the other hand, negative expressions will pertain to be sad or angry with the thoughts delivered by others on certain issue. For generating a good trend out of the social media content, the necessity for an automatic classifier becomes necessary to scale back the time for analysing the large volume of data and rising potency of the analysis method. This handiness of information ends up in various data services, tools and analytics platforms; hence these need researchers to program analytics in an exceeding language like Python.

The Sentiment analysis primarily tries to evaluate entirely different aspects of language that facilitate individuals to search out valuable data from great deal of unstructured information. It is a rising thought within which entirely different human emotions are measured from collected tweets or comments. It allows us to extract opinions and nostalgic feelings of every individual. To know people's opinion on an event, it is necessary to develop an automatic system that analyse an enormous quantity of information and produce desired result to a certain level of accuracy and it should be acceptable and relevant.

In the internet, people use journal posts and forums for enhancing merchandise similarly they used to share their views and thoughts on a

particular event. However, it becomes a significant challenge to perform such kinds of analysis on an enormous data. A numerous events occur often in our society, therefore, it is impractical to manually analyse each event and predict its future impact. It is extremely arduous for the computing machines to automatically extract the gist and tone of content as individual conveys many things in various ways. The sentiment analysis is proved to be terribly helpful once the computer Programme results have been analysed. This reduces the efforts needed to go through enormous amount of documents to get associate opinion concerning the nature of the contents extracted from the social media.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Twitter is one among the evolving social media that, on average, hosts around two hundred million tweets per day. Tweets typically correspond to infinite range of merchandise, services, social problems, news, incidents and reviews. Further, individuals additionally comment and share their views regarding tweets referring to numerous problems. Twitter share these tweets in an exceedingly distinctive method, it is not easy to categorize the content of the tweets based on its essence[1].

Facebook is one the foremost widespread social media network that started evolving in 2004. Individuals use Facebook for many functions — like posting reviews concerning products or services on dedicated pages; vote on completely different types of polls launched by users. Facebook supports 5 differing kinds of post: standing, video, link, image and music [2]. This information is extremely helpful for analysis. Some individuals use posts often to update their standing to share their mood, thoughts, activities, criticism, likes and dislikes concerning any connected event that are related to them. This medium not solely is a supply of expressing for huge variety of users, however it has additionally became a business for a more individuals.

The popularity of YouTube is due to easy use and eases of those systems for the creation, collaboration and sharing of resources like images or videos, even by non-technical users[3]. The current YouTube usage statistics indicate the approximate scale of the location at the time of this writing there unit of measurement quite one billion distinctive users viewing video content, observance over half-dozen billion hours of video monthly. Also, YouTube accounts for 20% of net traffic and 10 % percent of total net traffic[9].

Natural language process (NLP) is a field of computing, computer science and linguistics

involved with the interactions between computers and human (natural) languages. Specifically, it is the method of extracting meaningful data from natural language input and producing natural language output. A TextBlob could be a Python (2 and 3) library for process textual information. It provides an easy Application Programming Interface (API) for diving into common natural language process tasks like part-of-speech tagging, phrase extraction, sentiment analysis, classification, translation and more.

III. METHODOLOGY

The design and method flow of varied tasks for analysing sentiments of social media dataset is shown in Figure 3.1. Firstly, training data collected from numerous sources is subjected to pre-processing to eliminate options that do not contribute to polarity detection. This training data is fed into sentiment analysis engine for classifying new dataset or test dataset. Secondly, the input question term is employed to fetch information from social media that polarity is to be detected. The sentiment analysis engine contains Naive Bayes classification formula that consults coaching information to calculate possibilities and predict the sentiment for given question term.

A. Data Extraction

Some of the popular social networks, are Facebook, Twitter and YouTube, make a proportion of their data accessible via APIs [5]. Although several social networking media sites give API's for scraping information, however a number of the subsequent sites specifically Bing, LinkedIn and Skypedon't enable information scraping. Based on the given search keyword, the tweets are extracted from social media like Twitter using Twitter API [5], Facebook using Facebook API [6], YouTube using YouTube API [6] and further more from RSS feeds, Blogs, news groups and chat services. The retrieved data is subjected to pre-processing.

Fig. 1. Architecture diagram

B. Pre-Processing

The importance of quality versus quantity of data in social media scraping and analytics cannot be overdone. In fact, several details of analytics models are outlined by the kinds and quality of the information. Naturally, unstructured data will be terribly noisy. Hence, data clean-up is a very important space in social media analytics [6]. The method of data clean-up might involve removing typographic errors or confirmative and correcting values against a proverbial list of entities. Specifically, text might contain misspelled words, quotations, program codes, further areas, further line breaks, special characters, foreign words and more. Thus to attain high-quality text mining [7], it is necessary to conduct data clean-up at the primary step spell checking, removing duplicates, finding and substitution of the text, dynamic case of the text, removing areas and non-printing characters from text, fixing numbers, range signs and outliers, fixing dates and times, reworking and rearranging columns, rows and table data that don't contribute considerably to predict the sentiment of the tweet.

C. Model Building

A. Training

For training, the required information that are collected from the various source of social media are first parsed and relevant features are extracted from it to create the feature vector [8]. This vector is employed to form a Feature List that could be a list of all the options of all the information things in dataset used for training, this list is stored as a computer file on secondary memory for additional use in classification.

2. Naive Bayes Classifier

The Naive Bayes classifier could be an easy probabilistic classifier that relies on Bayes theorem with robust and naïve independence assumptions [10]. Despite the naïve style and simple assumptions that this system uses, Naive Bayes performs well in several advanced real-world issues. It is typically outperformed by alternative techniques like boosted trees, random forests, liquid ecstasy Entropy, Support Vector Machines and many other tools but Naive Bayes classifier is extremely efficient since it is less computationally intensive in each central processing unit and memory [11] and it needs a little quantity of training data. Moreover, the training time with Naive Bayes is considerably less as against different ways [9]. The Naive Bayes classifier is a general purpose, easy to implement and works well for a variety of applications. It classifies knowledge in 2 steps:

- Training step exploit the training samples, the strategy estimates the parameters of a probability distribution, assuming features are conditionally independent, given the class.

- Analysis step for any unseen test sample, the analysis find the posterior probability of that training data for each class. The method then classifies the test sample according to the largest posterior probability.

Using the Naïve Bayes classifier, the probability for a text to belong to each of the training data test can be classified. The class with the very best chance for the given tweet wins [12], the test data is pre-processed and a vector of test data is generated. This test data is then fed into Naive Bayes classifier along with the training data, now the classifier get polarity of the highest probability.

IV. RESULTS

A. Experimental Setup

Many popular scientific analytics libraries and tools are developed to supply support for sourcing, looking and analysing text. The Python language can be used for natural language detection, title and content extraction, question matching and, once utilized in conjunction with a module like scikit-learn, it may be trained to perform sentiment analysis mistreatment Naïve Bayes classifier [13].

Text analysis tools are used for tongue process and text analysis. There is a variety of freely accessible tools that are developed by educational teams and non-governmental organizations for sourcing, looking and analysing. A variety of open-source text analytics tools are available, especially for sentiment analysis. A popular text analysis tool, which is also open source, is Python TextBlob [1], which includes open-source Python modules, linguistic data and documentation for text analytics.

B. Comparison and Analysis

The data used for training as well as for testing data are collected from the social media like Twitter, Facebook, YouTube and RSS Feed. The results of experiments are used create the training set and data set for analysis, it is necessary to label the tweets supported the sentiment they carry

- Sentiment subjectivity - whether a sentiment expresses an opinion or is factual without expressing a positive or negative opinion.
- Sentiment polarity - whether a sentiment in a text is positive, neutral or negative.

Perhaps, the foremost troublesome analysis is distinguishing sentiment polarity and strength - the words wonderful, elegant, amazing, cool and more considered as positive comments, neutral is denoted by fine or ok, similarly negative comments can be referred using words like horrible, disgusting, poor, flaky, sucks and so on. A preferred approach is to assign polarity scores as 1, 0, -1 where 1 is positive, 0 is neutral and -1 is

negative. [15]. The polarity score of the text is that the total of orientation lots of all ‘opinion’ words found. However, there are various potential issues during this oversimplified approach, like negation [16]. One technique of estimating sentiment polarity of the text is purpose wise mutual data

(PMI) a live of association utilized in scientific theory and statistics. Furthermore, Table I shows some of the collected tweets classification and prediction along with the score value and the values are plotted in the following graph shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 1 show the volume of tweet extracted.

Table I
 Classification and Prediction of Tweets

S.no.	Tweet	Positive	Negative	Neutral	Prediction
1	RT @YuviWorld: Yuvians, #HappyBirthdayYuvi is now Trending on number 3 in India. Do a surgical strike.. bring it on the top before 12'o clo...	0.7	0.0	0.3	Neutral
2	RT @muglikar_: Dosto, B4 any feku journo comes up with data as to "how unsafe digital payments are" here is a surgical strike on t...	0.4	0.6	0.5	Negative
3	Surgical strike led to abrupt change of ISI chief in Pakistan https://t.co/XR5EO45Kll	0.5	0.0	0.5	Neutral
4	RT @vickynanjappa: Surgical strike led to abrupt change of ISI chief in Pakistan https://t.co/jVjRxLWwLo # via @oneindia	0.6	0.0	0.4	Neutral
5	SWhat Famous And Non-Famous People Talked About Indian Surgical Strike ? https://t.co/vT1tOHeCY0	0.7	0.3	0.3	Positive
6	RT @EconomicTimes: Note ban no surgical strike on black money: Hardik Patel https://t.co/TfEaF4VVit https://t.co/mahHkJA1Mk	0.6	0.0	0.4	Neutral
7	RT @muglikar_: Dosto, B4 any feku journo comes up with data as to "how unsafe digital payments are" here is a surgical strike on that artic...	0.5	0.5	0.5	Negative
8	RT @vickynanjappa: Surgical strike led to abrupt change of ISI chief in Pakistan https://t.co/jVjRxLWwLo # via @oneindia	0.6	0.0	0.4	Neutral

Fig. 1 Volume of Extracted Tweet

Fig. 2 Tweet Classification and Prediction

There may be more than one issue that have an effect on the prediction. Some of the bottlenecks faced during the analysis are limitations of social

media APIs, lot of spam and noise included in randomly picked tweets.

Similarly, predictions on 8 more keywords, their positive, negative and neutral value scores are listed in the Table II. And based on those values, a graph is plotted to show the prediction in the Fig. 3.

Table II
 Classification and Prediction of Keywords

S. no.	Keyword	Positive %	Negative %	Neutral%
1	Surgical Strike executed by BJP government	16.7	18.6	64.7
2	Digital India is useful?	13.9	39.0	47.1
3	H-1B visa: Won't allow US workers to be replaced, says Donald Trump	12.5	62.5	25.0
4	User Review : iPhone 7 reach in India	34.4	6.7	59.0
5	Donald Trump presidential campaign and office	38.1	15.0	46.9
6	Telecom Product : Reliance JIO	53.3	5.9	40.8
7	P & G Product : Patanjali	12.2	6.9	81.0
8	Customer Review : Walmart Service	30.7	16.6	52.7

Fig. 3 Keyword Classification and Prediction

V. CONCLUSION

As mentioned, the simple availability of API provided by Twitter, Facebook and News services has led to an ‘explosion’ of data services and software tools for crawling and performing sentiment analysis on social media analytics platforms. This paper surveys a number of the social media software system tools, and for completeness introduced social media scraping, data clean-up and sentiment analysis. The largest concern is that corporate (like Facebook, YouTube, Twitter) are increasingly restrict the limiting access to their data. The accuracy results created by the engine victimization for negative and positive sentiment were highest. Machine Learning is associate degree ever evolving field with newer and enhance d algorithms. These algorithms are often wont to push the envelope even more with regards to hurry, area and accuracy parameters.

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